

IMPROVEMENT OF DRILLING FLUID FOR CONSTRUCTION OF WELLS IN ARCTIC SHELF WATER.

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Key words : *clay sandstones , inhibitor , montmorillonite clay , hydration , deformation , dispersion , water Arctic shelf.*

Annotation : *book and field information-based In the waters of the Arctic shelf, the well to build his own special geological and technical conditions, unstable mud in the mines inhibitor drilling from liquids to use the efficiency of seeing will be released.*

Researchers most of them in the borehole insults and falls appear to be drilling liquid clay own into the resulting floor with a physicist and chemical mutual effect process with connects

Khar another like braking doer drilling from liquids use exercise that 's all showed that from them some mining and geological in data circumstances use efficiency another in data circumstances wells successful drilling guarantee Not Maybe

liquid drilling dispersion ability determination method inhibitor drilling in liquid clay flooring small particles colloid to the situation transition intensity to reduce based on this chemistry processing from providing before and after washing liquid technological in the parameters in contrast is expressed.

Fluid drilling experiments in the laboratory STO 7.07-2010 "Drilling fluids technological parameters definition of the methodology is presented in" Methods and from the instructions used without increased

Gil minerals to water-based drilling fluid with mutual effect processes to teach and inhibitory supplements choose dedicated.

Well conditions washing liquid clay stones arrange found wall surface with direct connection will be In this well to well near zone bound moisture form with distinguishable three layered body as kind can be

The first in the layer is osmotic and capillary strength to holding standing empty bound water rule makes This layer is washing in the liquid the solute absorbs and the solvent itself (water) separated out the output pressure under the influence of shrinking.

The second layer of dirt particles surface active centers next to many layered adsorbed moisture with a pronounced weak water-bound existence with described. This layer clay floor humidity P/P_s is relative at the vapor pressure of the sample, the maximum hygroscopicity from humidity does not exceed - 0.95...1. Such in this case category water molecules clay surface fields from effect Fully protected and different substances with mutual Effect Do It This Not Maybe

The third layer of drilling liquid to the effect did not meet and natural moisture (strong bound and weak bound moisture) that keeps the clay floor to be his to appreciate the harvest to be and appear to be conditions depend

Moisturizing processes development from the first layer to the well to fall down and drilling liquid with immediately contact who the second layer surface opens and the same, that's all the process of the

first layer is repeated. Therefore, juicy drilling liquid with direct connection was a well on the wall boundary layer of the membrane has a function, however, the ideal level is not enough The first layer is moistening softening and the next layer is to get wet the road is not put for the well on the wall mortar and clay floor between the artificial half permeable membrane Create need to

If the drilling liquid is a liquid phase as non-polar of the liquid if used, then large molecules for the "inner" surface of the minerals to have if there is clay floors organize found wells on the walls moisturizing and moisturizing stress development prevention can be obtained do not slip to the fence access is possible not Such molecules adsorption (usually monomolecular) only external on surfaces happen will be

This clay-based oil lubrication (OBM) condition satisfies their structural part of the clay floor with contact in the process of half-permeable membrane crop makes Such of the membrane only water molecules it will pass as long as only from clay moisture change to take will come this is ion exchange and adsorption reaction c depends on other physical and chemical processes effect exclusion make enable gives

However , environment protection do and mining work safety point of view from the point of view of MBP drilling of Russia 's Arctic sea in the waters of the use is prohibited .

Dirt sex with on the connection was half permeable membrane receiving methods one low molecular weight organic did not happen to use electrolytes. Such non-electrolytes are glycols, dioxane alcohols, mono-, di-, triethanolamine and others. Simple under the circumstances, they are liquid in the form of eating and water with a good reciprocal effect makes

Such reagents between oil and gas in the industry most celebrity various polyglycols (PG). modifications, in particular polyethylene-, polypropylene-, polyalkylene glycols and their technical mixtures.

Oxygen atom negative inductive effect due to PG molecules strong polarization with described, from this as a result they are Minus charged to the surface proximity is So changed glycol molecules chemical composition of their surface dirt active in places to adsorption opportunity gives A special result like this regions screening to do, clay minerals moisturizing and swelling processes suppressed.

used books list

1. Shaimanova R.S., Urazov M.K., Yuldosheva D.N., Shaimanova N.Kh. Development technologies drilling with hydraulic motors in salt blood conditions. Multidisciplinary scientific journal and No. 1. S. Technologies. 5-6.
2. Shaimanova R.S., Urazov M.K., Yuldosheva D.N., Shaimanova N.Kh Development technologies drilling hydraulic motors in salt blood conditions. Multidisciplinary journal of science and technology. No. 1. S. 20-22.
3. Shaimanova R.S., Urazov M.K., Yuldosheva D.N., Shaimanova N.Kh. Development technologies drilling with hydraulic motors in salt blood conditions. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science Oath Technology. No. 1. S. 23-25.
4. Shaimanova R.S., Urazov M.K., Yuldosheva D.N., Shaimanova N.Kh. Development technologies drilling with hydraulic motors in salt blood conditions. Multidisciplinary journal of science and technology. No. 1. S. 26-29.
5. Shaimanova R. S. , Urazov M. No. , Yuldosheva D. N. Shaymanova N. H. development technology Burenia c hydraulic motor c conditions Solenoid TV series Multi-profile scientific and technical journal. No. 1. S. 5-6.

6. Muradov MM, Mukhitdinov UD, Urozov MK, Khudoyorov XO. Comparative studies of the composition and properties of CMT at different degrees of polymerization. // Scientific and technical practical journal of composite materials 2018 No. 1 - p. 57-58 (02.00.00 #4)
7. Mukhitdinov Yu.D., Murodov M.M., Urozov M.K. Technology for obtaining high-quality cellulose from sunflower stems and fiber waste from textile enterprises. //Composite materials Scientific and technical practical journal 2018 No. 1.- P. 65-66 (02.00.00 #4)
8. Turdiboeva N.Yu., Murodov M.M., Urozov M.K. Development of technology for obtaining cellulose from plants and production of Na - carboxymethylcellulose on its basis . Scientific, technical and practical journal of composite materials. - Tashkent, 2018. - No. 3. P.36 (02.00.00 #4)
9. Urozov M.K., Turdiboeva N.Yu., Murodov M.M. Development of technology for the production of cellulose from vegetable safflower and based on carboxymethylcellulose . //Scientific-technical and practical journal of composite materials. - Tashkent, 2018.- No. 3. p.58 (02.00.00 #4)